

ISic3628

Honorific inscription for a benefactor

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object

fragment

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Calacte

Place of origin (modern)

Caronia

Provenance

Found in a field in Caronia

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Caronia, Deposito della Soprintendenza BB.CC. di Messina, inventory Caronia 25274

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 12.7 cm

Width 14 cm

Depth 3.5-4 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1-3: 6 mm

Line 4-14: 4 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: Not measured mm

Text

1. Ἐπὶ ἀμφιπόλου (?) e.g. Ἀπολλωνίου τοῦ Ἀπολλοδώρου
2. Ἐλωρείου (?) μηνὸς ἐν]δεκάται προσ(άτας)
3. [τᾶς βουλαῖς e.g. Ξένις Ξενίσκου Πλη·
4. [ἔδοξε τᾶι ἀλίαι καθὰ κ]αὶ τᾶι συγκλήτῳ καὶ τᾶι βουλαῖ·
5. [ἐπειδὴ? --]ις ἄνδρου Τηλ φανερός ἐστι ἀμῶν
6. [φίλος, ἄξια πράσων] καὶ λόγῳ καὶ ἔργῳ, δίκαιον δέ
7. [ἐστὶ διαμένειν αὐ]τοῦ μνάμαν, ποιεῖσθαι δὲ ὅσα τὰ
8. [? νόμιμα καὶ εὐεργ]έταν αὐτὸν εἶμειν τοῦ δάμου,
9. [ὅπως φανερόν ἦι πᾶσι] τοῖς ἐπιγινο[μέν]οις, ὅτι [τ]ο[ῖς]
10. [εὐεργετεῖν αἰρουμέν]οις τὸ κοινὸν δύναται χάριτας
11. [καὶ τιμὰς ἀπονέμειν] τὰς καταξίας· τὸ δὲ ἀλίασμα
12. [ἐπιγράψασθαι εἰς χαλκ]ῶματα δύο καὶ ἀναθέμειν
13. [τὸ μὲν ἐν τῷ ἱερῷ τοῦ Ἀ]πόλλωνος, τὸ δὲ δόμειν
14. [αὐτῷ ὑπόμναμα τᾶς πο]τὶ τὸν δᾶμον εὐ[νοίας· τοὺς δὲ]
15. [ταμίας ἐξοδιάξει -----]

Apparatus

Text of Manganaro 2011

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645701

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